

Animal Model with Fixed Effects of block & population

FINAL MODEL with Fixed effects – USED IN MS

```
# Load model output
load(file = "animModel_1M_thin5K_x6_fixedEffects.RData")

UP_FE_model_chains <- model_6chains

### Summarize each run of model
summary(model_6chains[[1]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21109.2
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4372  0.1441  0.8291    180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam    0.1416  0.0806  0.2002    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units      1      1      1      0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.65712 -0.82068 -0.49890    539 <0.006 **
## block2      0.09148 -0.04482  0.22575    180  0.178
## popF:M      0.56912  0.40694  0.71347    180 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.81342  0.56477  0.98440    180 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.45111  1.22249  1.72442    180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[2]])
```

```

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21107.58
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4384  0.1566  0.7376    180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1369  0.08373  0.1916    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units        1        1        1        0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.65374 -0.81598 -0.52138    180 <0.006 **
## block2      0.08740 -0.01833  0.23314    243  0.111
## popF:M      0.56911  0.40969  0.73991    180 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.80303  0.59481  0.97348    401 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.44418  1.20118  1.65416    180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[3]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21107.21
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4422  0.1879  0.7641    180
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp

```

```

## dam    0.1352  0.06954  0.1806    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units         1         1         1         0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.66848 -0.83429 -0.52553    180 <0.006 **
## block2       0.10274 -0.01091  0.23398    180 0.0889 .
## popF:M       0.57175  0.39572  0.73748    180 <0.006 **
## popM:F       0.79937  0.59837  1.00476    180 <0.006 **
## popM:M       1.44624  1.25473  1.71622    180 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[4]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21109.55
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4274  0.1448  0.7489    222.5
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam         0.135  0.07349  0.1929    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units         1         1         1         0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.65829 -0.78512 -0.52003    180 <0.006 **
## block2       0.09154 -0.02475  0.23178    180  0.156
## popF:M       0.58223  0.43610  0.73572    180 <0.006 **
## popM:F       0.80438  0.58764  1.03498    180 <0.006 **
## popM:M       1.44289  1.18718  1.63554    180 <0.006 **

```

```

## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[5]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21110.41
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4417  0.1797  0.838    121.5
##
##      ~dam
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1382  0.0792  0.2011    180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units        1        1        1        0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##      post.mean  l-95% CI  u-95% CI  eff.samp  pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.666439 -0.812585 -0.513725    180.0 <0.006 **
## block2      0.103099 -0.001531  0.232716    180.0 0.0667 .
## popF:M      0.568120  0.395314  0.753041    180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.808426  0.631088  1.039577    180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.453498  1.230064  1.716957    134.3 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

summary(model_6chains[[6]])

##
## Iterations = 100001:995001
## Thinning interval = 5000
## Sample size = 180
##
## DIC: 21104.11
##
## G-structure: ~animal
##
##      post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## animal    0.4559  0.1467  0.7936    180

```

```

##
##           ~dam
##
##   post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## dam      0.1377  0.06987  0.1895      180
##
## R-structure: ~units
##
##   post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp
## units       1       1       1       0
##
## Location effects: sex ~ block + pop
##
##           post.mean l-95% CI u-95% CI eff.samp pMCMC
## (Intercept) -0.66659 -0.84971 -0.53161   180.0 <0.006 **
## block2      0.09068 -0.05367  0.21518   463.4  0.156
## popF:M      0.57909  0.42888  0.76733   180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:F      0.82074  0.63847  1.03744   180.0 <0.006 **
## popM:M      1.45830  1.22432  1.68535   180.0 <0.006 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

### Summarize 6 chains
animCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
animCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)
animCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
animCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
animCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
animCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

ES_VCV_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)
ES_VCV_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

library(dplyr)

##
## Attaching package: 'dplyr'

## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':
##
##   filter, lag

## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':
##
##   intersect, setdiff, setequal, union

```

```

resultsVCV_UP_FE <- bind_rows(animCh1, animCh2, animCh3, animCh4, animCh5,
animCh6)
ES_VCV_UP_FE <- bind_rows(ES_VCV_Ch1, ES_VCV_Ch2, ES_VCV_Ch3, ES_VCV_Ch4,
ES_VCV_Ch5,
  ES_VCV_Ch6)

SolCh1 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)
SolCh2 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
SolCh3 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
SolCh4 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
SolCh5 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)
SolCh6 <- as.data.frame(model_6chains[[6]]$Sol)

ES_Sol_Ch1 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[1]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch2 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[2]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch3 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[3]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch4 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[4]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch5 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[5]]$Sol)
ES_Sol_Ch6 <- effectiveSize(model_6chains[[6]]$Sol)

resultsSol_UP_FE <- bind_rows(SolCh1, SolCh2, SolCh3, SolCh4, SolCh5, SolCh6)
ES_Sol_UP_FE <- bind_rows(ES_Sol_Ch1, ES_Sol_Ch2, ES_Sol_Ch3, ES_Sol_Ch4,
ES_Sol_Ch5,
  ES_Sol_Ch6)

ES_Sol_UP_FE

## # A tibble: 6 × 5
##   `(Intercept)` block2 `popF:M` `popM:F` `popM:M`
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 539. 180 180 180 180.
## 2 180 243. 180 401. 180
## 3 180 180 180 180 180
## 4 180. 180 180 180 180
## 5 180 180 180 180 134.
## 6 180 463. 180 180 180

ES_VCV_UP_FE

## # A tibble: 6 × 3
##   animal dam units
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 180 180 0
## 2 180 180 0
## 3 180 180 0
## 4 223. 180 0
## 5 121. 180 0
## 6 180 180. 0

heidel.diag(as.mcmc(resultsVCV_UP_FE))

```

```

##
##      Stationarity start      p-value
##      test      iteration
## animal passed      1      0.880
## dam   passed      1      0.405
## units failed      NA      NA
##
##      Halfwidth Mean  Halfwidth
##      test
## animal passed      0.440 0.01023
## dam   passed      0.137 0.00186
## units <NA>      NA      NA

### BELOW USED TO CHECK MIXING OF CHAINS IN PARALLEL
animalChains_UP_FE <- cbind(animCh1, animCh2, animCh3, animCh4, animCh5,
animCh6)
names(animalChains_UP_FE) <- c("anim1", "dam1", "unit1", "anim2", "dam2",
"unit2",
  "anim3", "dam3", "unit3", "anim4", "dam4", "unit4", "anim5", "dam5",
"unit5",
  "anim6", "dam6", "unit6")
base <- ggplot(animalChains_UP_FE, aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_FE)),
  y = anim1, group = 3)) + geom_path()

base + geom_path(aes(x = as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_FE)), y =
anim2, group = 1),
  colour = "blue") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_FE)),
  y = anim3, group = 1), colour = "green") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_FE)),
  y = anim4, group = 1), colour = "red") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_FE)),
  y = anim5, group = 1), colour = "orange") + geom_path(aes(x =
as.numeric(row.names(animalChains_UP_FE)),
  y = anim6, group = 1), colour = "maroon1")

```


Check autocorrs

```
autocorr(model_6chains[[1]]$VCV)
```

```
## , , animal
##
##           animal      dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.58271571  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.054352958 -0.04208995  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.097402124  0.09055371  NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.204954704  0.19827276  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.007236636  0.01897490  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##           animal      dam units
## Lag 0      -0.58271571  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000    0.01436396  0.070514008  NaN
## Lag 25000   0.02862488  0.014541157  NaN
## Lag 50000   0.07698063 -0.119677659  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.03555319  0.006419862  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##           animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
```

```

## Lag 50000      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000    NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[2]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##           animal           dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.44300026   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.035095293 -0.01407913   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.007488318 -0.05184381   NaN
## Lag 50000  0.003038657 -0.02986201   NaN
## Lag 250000 0.075409951  0.06489386   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##           animal           dam units
## Lag 0      -0.44300026  1.00000000   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.05663399  0.03598140   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.05999090 -0.04409280   NaN
## Lag 50000  0.04481894  0.03399457   NaN
## Lag 250000 0.02112843 -0.06116688   NaN
##
## , , units
##
##           animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN   NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN   NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[3]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##           animal           dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.45160293   NaN
## Lag 5000   0.03433012  0.06086148   NaN
## Lag 25000 -0.00435019  0.04749065   NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.00307553 -0.05176623   NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.07317264  0.03095826   NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##           animal           dam units
## Lag 0      -0.45160293  1.00000000   NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.07955364 -0.05654453   NaN
## Lag 25000  0.06566465  0.06448118   NaN
## Lag 50000  0.02068926  0.09204597   NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.05682328  0.05654167   NaN

```

```

##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[4]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.4399514858  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.108407099 -0.0171651873  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.008882667  0.0246868299  NaN
## Lag 50000 -0.047830885  0.0095339138  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.018294367 -0.0001246446  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.43995149  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000    0.20357512 -0.05317736  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.07540848 -0.08278778  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.04782947 -0.01498504  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.02064424  0.04721359  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000  NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000 NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[5]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.000000000 -0.39678075  NaN
## Lag 5000    0.19151129 -0.26473409  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.04033872  0.03633716  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.02554579 -0.07555763  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.01095034 -0.03105807  NaN
##
## , , dam

```

```

##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.39678075  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000    0.04641123  0.05676941  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.12588035  0.01594493  NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.02487713  0.13205757  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.06658101  0.02836392  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000    NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000  NaN NaN  NaN

autocorr(model_6chains[[6]]$VCV)

## , , animal
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      1.00000000 -0.42999077  NaN
## Lag 5000   -0.02536312 -0.07689725  NaN
## Lag 25000  0.05959056 -0.10117682  NaN
## Lag 50000  0.03187327  0.11634323  NaN
## Lag 250000 -0.05279657 -0.01256873  NaN
##
## , , dam
##
##          animal          dam units
## Lag 0      -0.42999077  1.00000000  NaN
## Lag 5000    0.21305422 -0.005720897  NaN
## Lag 25000  -0.05385320  0.061432787  NaN
## Lag 50000  -0.04432668 -0.004075066  NaN
## Lag 250000 0.08729584  0.029445230  NaN
##
## , , units
##
##          animal dam units
## Lag 0      NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 5000    NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 25000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 50000   NaN NaN  NaN
## Lag 250000  NaN NaN  NaN

require(QGglmm)
n <- length(resultsSol_UP_FE$(Intercept))
mu <- mean(resultsSol_UP_FE$(Intercept))
va <- mean(resultsVCV_UP_FE$animal)

```

```

vd <- mean(resultsVCV_UP_FE$dam)
vp <- mean(rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_FE))

QGparams(mu = mu, var.a = va, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit")
## [1] "Using the closed forms for a Binomial1 - probit model."
##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.a.obs   h2.obs
## 1 0.3401071 0.2244343 0.02294545 0.1022368

QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = vd, var.p = vp, model = "binom1.probit")
## [1] "Using a semi-closed form for a binom1.probit model."
## Warning in QGicc(mu = mu, var.comp = vd, var.p = vp, model =
## "binom1.probit"): Some component (var.comp.obs) are not totally
##   from a closed form solution: an integral is computed
##   mean.obs  var.obs  var.comp.obs  icc.obs
## 1 0.3401071 0.2244343 0.007193578 0.03205205

library(purrr)
X1 <- model_6chains[[1]][["X"]]
t <- model_6chains[[1]][["Sol"]]

predict1 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[1]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[1]][["Sol"]][.,
]))

predict2 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[2]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[2]][["Sol"]][.,
]))

predict3 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[3]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[3]][["Sol"]][.,
]))

predict4 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[4]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[4]][["Sol"]][.,
]))

predict5 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[5]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[5]][["Sol"]][.,
]))

predict6 <- map(1:nrow(model_6chains[[6]][["Sol"]]), ~as.vector(X1 %*%
model_6chains[[6]][["Sol"]][.,
]))

predict <- c(predict1, predict2, predict3, predict4, predict5, predict6)

```

```

paramsB_UP_FE <- pmap_dfr(list(predict = predict, var.a =
resultsVCV_UP_FE$animal,
  var.p = rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_FE) - 1), QGparams, model =
"binom1.probit", verbose = FALSE)

### predict is a list the length of the sample size & each element of the
list
### has the same length as the length of the fixed effect matrix

mean(paramsB_UP_FE[["h2.obs"]])

## [1] 0.1442554

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(paramsB_UP_FE[["h2.obs"]]))

##          lower      upper
## var1 0.07409875 0.2296024
## attr("Probability")
## [1] 0.95

## Heritability on Liability scale
herit_liab_UP_FE <- resultsVCV_UP_FE$animal/rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_FE)
mean(herit_liab_UP_FE)

## [1] 0.2716856

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(herit_liab_UP_FE))

##          lower      upper
## var1 0.1357636 0.4367051
## attr("Probability")
## [1] 0.95

compute_varpred <- function(beta, design_matrix) {
  var(as.vector(design_matrix %*% beta))
}
vf_UP_FE <- apply(resultsSol_UP_FE, 1, compute_varpred, design_matrix = X1)
herit_UP_FE <- resultsVCV_UP_FE$animal/(rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_FE) + vf_UP_FE)
mean(herit_UP_FE)

## [1] 0.2289126

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(herit_UP_FE))

##          lower      upper
## var1 0.1144196 0.3620669
## attr("Probability")
## [1] 0.95

##### Below is from deVillemereuil2021 (zotero) - tutorial 2, Section 4.2, p.
37

```

```
### Heritability on Observed scale pmap_dfr is a purr function that works
### similarly to mapply
library(purrr)
paramsB_UP_FE <- pmap_dfr(list(mu = resultsSol_UP_FE$(Intercept), var.a =
  resultsVCV_UP_FE$animal,
  var.p = rowSums(resultsVCV_UP_FE) + vf_UP_FE), QGparams, model =
  "binom1.probit",
  verbose = FALSE)
mean(paramsB_UP_FE[["h2.obs"]])

## [1] 0.0903073

HPDinterval(as.mcmc(paramsB_UP_FE[["h2.obs"]]))

##           lower      upper
## var1 0.03448306 0.1430949
## attr(,"Probability")
## [1] 0.95

plot(as.mcmc(resultsVCV_UP_FE$animal))
```



```
heidel.diag(as.mcmc(resultsVCV_UP_FE))

##
## Stationarity test start iteration p-value
## animal passed 1 0.880
## dam passed 1 0.405
```

```
## units failed      NA      NA
##
##      Halfwidth Mean  Halfwidth
##      test
## animal passed    0.440 0.01023
## dam   passed    0.137 0.00186
## units <NA>      NA      NA

library(coda)
library(lattice)
densityplot(as.mcmc(paramsB_UP_FE[["h2.obs"]]))
```



```
h2_UP_FE <- as.data.frame(as.mcmc(paramsB_UP_FE[["h2.obs"]]))
```

```
### FROM: https://github.com/devillemereuil/prior-MCMCglmm/blob/master/priors.R
```

```
library(mvtnorm)
library(MCMCglmm)
library(ggplot2)
library(progress)
```

```
## ----- Prior model for monovariate
```

```
## Parameters
```

```
K <- 1e+05 # Number of iterations
nu <- 1000 # nu parameter = 1000 for default prior
alpha.mu <- 0 # alpha.mu parameter = 0 for default prior
```

```
alpha.V <- 1 # alpha.V parameter = 1 for default prior

### my initial informed prior was nu=1000, alpha.mu=0.6, alpha.V=0.05 IP2 is
### nu=5, alpha.mu=0.7, alpha.V=0.05

## Prior for extended parameter Va Variance of eta
pr_var_eta <- rIW(n = K, V = diag(1), nu = nu)[, 1]
# Alpha
pr_alpha <- rnorm(K, alpha.mu, sqrt(alpha.V))
# Resulting prior on Va
pr_var_a <- (pr_alpha^2) * pr_var_eta

## Prior for residual variance Essentially useless for a binary trait, as fix
=
## 1... but keeping it in case we want to remove fix = 1
pr_var_r <- rIW(n = K, V = diag(1), nu = 1, fix = 1)[, 1]

## Resulting prior for heritability
pr_herit_Chi1 <- pr_var_a/(pr_var_a + pr_var_r)

## Plotting the density of the prior
qplot(x = pr_herit_Chi1, geom = "density")
```



```
prior_plot_noFE <- ggplot() + geom_density(aes(x = pr_herit_Chi1)) + labs(x =
"Prob. Heritabililty",
y = "Density") + xlim(0, 1) + theme_classic() + theme(axis.text =
element_text(size = rel(2)),
```

```
axis.title.x = element_text(size = rel(2.5)), axis.title.y =  
element_text(size = rel(2.5)),  
axis.line.x.bottom = element_line(size = 1), axis.line.y.left =  
element_line(size = 1),  
panel.background = element_rect(fill = "transparent", colour = NA),  
plot.background = element_rect(fill = "transparent",  
colour = NA))  
prior_plot_noFE
```

